

**THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY MINUTES AT THE
LESSONS**

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Brief abstract. The article deals with the efficient forming of the physical training and sports lessons, raising of the interest to physical training lessons in students in education institutions, forming of the habits, knowledge, ability to different kinds of sport and displaying interest to different sports competitions in this area.

Keywords: sports activities, communication skills, personal development, prosocial skills.

Sports is a great opportunity to encourage all students to be enthusiastic about sports, even the non-athletically inclined. The importance of sports in class cannot be underestimated, and getting students involved in sports make them healthier and happier too. In this article, we're going to take a look at the many benefits of class sports and discover some great ideas for you [1].

Physical Health. Playing sports can make you stronger and healthier, as well as contributing to lower obesity rates. Currently, scientists point out that, one in three children leaves primary school obese or overweight. Athletes tend to have lower body mass indexes, but non-athlete participants will still benefit from developing muscles and burning calories. Long-term, active people tend to have lower rates of diabetes and high blood pressure. Exercising regularly through sports programs could also contribute to better heart and lung function. Learning to play sports as a child might carry over into being a more active adult; some sports tend to have a more lasting impact from childhood into adulthood, for example,

football and hockey. As well as increasing stamina and strength, regular exercise can make students more energetic, and therefore, more able to concentrate in the classroom [3].

Mental Health. According to the Faculty of Sport and Exercise Medicine, UK, “Physical activity can increase self-esteem and reduce depression and anxiety in children. We also know that physical activity performed in an outdoor space can improve cognitive performance, self-esteem and reduce anxiety and symptoms related to attention deficit disorder.” The benefits of sport and physical activity on our mental health are endless: improved mood, decreased chance of depression and anxiety, and a better and more balanced lifestyle ... Any kind of physical activity can boost mental wellbeing – from swimming to walking and yoga to dance. This means that even students who aren’t competitive and don’t enjoy traditional sports, can get involved and take part in physical activity, leading to potential improvements in physical and mental wellbeing. Why not provide some lunchtime taster sessions for activities such as yoga, dance and quidditch?

Learning. The importance of sports can also be seen in improving learning and development. As mentioned above, taking part in regular physical exercise can give students more energy and therefore more likely to concentrate on classroom learning. The Novak Djokovic Foundation also emphasizes the importance of sports for children, stating benefits such as: - Kids’ character and moral principles are formed through fair play. Moreover, children who are actively engaged in sports can be good role models for their peers from school and their communities.

- Playing sports enables them to create friendships they otherwise might not have formed. For example, the friendships professional athletes create on the field remain intact even when they are not playing sports, and often last a lifetime [5].

- Sports bring people together from all over the world, regardless of their nationality, religion, culture, or skin colour.

- Teamwork and benefits of social interaction among children are best seen

in sports. Kids learn they are part of a team that requires the same effort from all members to succeed, as well as how to win with class, and lose with dignity.

- They view competitions on and off the field as opportunities to learn from their success and failure. In addition, losing often motivates kids to work even harder next time.

- They learn to respect authority, rules, team colleagues and opponents.

Sports days are ideal for highlighting the importance of teamwork and taking part, even if the activities are outside of some pupils' comfort zones. In the run-up to your sports day, you could use your Physical Education lessons to get students to set personal bests for the events that you will be running at your event. This gives students an achievable goal to aim for on Sports Day so that even those who aren't athletic can feel the success of setting a faster time than their previous ones. You can also tie Sports Day into Growth Mindset; encouraging students who have not achieved what they hoped to, to learn from a potentially negative experience and use it to progress in the future [7].

Fun Ideas. Fun at the Seaside. On a 50-metre running track, you will need to lay out a rubber ring for each pupil on the 10-metre line, a pair of armbands each on the 20-metre line, a mask and snorkel each on the 30-metre line and a beach ball on the 40-metre line. Each child should start the race wearing a pair of flippers and collect and put on each of the additional items as they run. Hopefully this will lead to a lot of laughter for the spectators.

Balloon Squeeze. Another task that requires good teamwork; in pairs students must get a balloon to the end of a 50-metre track by squashing it between their chests or tummies. They must not use their hands or feet to move the balloon and if they drop it they will have to go back to the beginning.

Bucket Head Challenge. This race is perfect for a hot summer day. Each student needs to hold a bucket of water on their head whilst completing a tricky

obstacle course, including going over hurdles, jumping through hoops and limboing under horizontal poles. The winner is not the person who completes the course the quickest but the student who has the most water left in their bucket at the end.

Jump the Line. Draw a line down the middle of the board. Draw sports of your choice, relevant to your students either side of the line. For example, draw a tennis racket and a baseball bat on the left and a swimming pool and a football on the right. Stick on paper pictures if you prefer. Name a sport and tell the children to stick out either their left arm or their right arm to indicate which side of the line the picture is. Say the words slowly once each and have the children stick out either a left arm or a right arm. This is a check to make sure everyone has understood the game. Now start saying the words quite quickly but not so fast the children get lost. Gradually accelerate. The fun is all in the pace of the game and keeping pupils on their toes. If you say each word slowly, then wait till every child is sticking out the correct arm, it will be totally boring. Those students who make some errors will still be hearing the words over and over again anyway. Make sure you call out words on the same side as well as alternating sides so the children never know which arm it will be. Then add in two more words and play with 6 words. Repeat words you see children don't know so well more often. The whole game from start to finish should take five to six minutes and should be played in silence.

Teach the sentence "I play tennis". The children will have a good grasp of the sports vocabulary by now so you can start to use some sentences such as, "Can you play tennis?" Or, "I play tennis." Relay Race is a simple game to practise saying short sentences. I suggest you make teams. It's easier to use the existing configuration of your class. So, if you have five rows of six children then have five teams of six. Each team will pass the relay from front to back or vice versa. We suggest that you pass down sentences such as "I can play tennis, I can play football, I can play golf." Give each team a different picture flashcard to pass

down. The first person holds their flashcard of a sport. When you say, “go” students pass the card to the person behind them saying, “I can play tennis.” This person takes the card and passes it to the one behind them saying, “I can play tennis.” Students keep going until the picture card reaches the end. At that point, the student at the end can bring the card up to the front – walking only (and watch out for bags and things in the aisles that can be tripped over). A little movement is good in class, but not too much with thirty students.

Writing games. Hangman. Now you could show your students how the words are written by playing hangman for a few minutes. Hopefully, you will get through all 8 new words in about 5-8 minutes. You do not want to play for longer than that. Tell the students that they must write down the correct spelling of each word during the game in their vocabulary notebooks – or wherever.

Speaking Games. Now you could try duck, duck, goose. Set up a four-beat rhythm with two of the sports words, such as tennis, tennis, golf. Golf is two beats; tennis is one beat. Have 5 potatoes or pieces of screwed up paper which are passed around the class as the students chant the rhythm. The potatoes should be evenly spread about the room. Tell them the route they must pass the potatoes. For example, up and down the rows or from side to side. After thirty seconds of chanting, say stop on “golf”. All the students holding a potato stand up and do a forfeit. This can be anything, such as naming a random vocabulary flashcard, doing a dance or doing 10-star jumps. You could put the children in two teams and whenever a child doing a forfeit correctly names the vocabulary, give a point to their team. Then set up the rhythm again but this time with two different sports words, such as football, football, swimming. Once the rhythm is going, tell the children to pass the potatoes and once again stop unpredictably and repeat the forfeits for whoever is holding the potatoes. Repeat this game until you have practised all the vocabulary. To keep good discipline, you can deduct a point from the team if a team member is misbehaving [9].

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